

The Semantic Alignment of H-FOAF, DOMAIN and DBLP Ontologies with Link Open Data for a Health Social Network

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to make collaborative networks of practitioners and researchers especially for healthcare community by using semantic web standards such as FOAF, etc. The proposed collaborative ontology modeling helps to resolve semantic alignment between distributed developed vocabularies/ontologies with domain ontology (cardiac-process) by using collaborative methodology. This collaborative ontology mechanism helps to find specific personnel who are involved in certain tasks, activities with assigned roles and involved in some research projects and attached with health-oriented social community. This approach also helps to publish domain factual knowledge with some link open data (LOD) resources, e.g. DBpedia for reusability.

Keywords: FOAF, SIOC, DBLP, Link Open Data, OWL, SPARQL.

1. INTRODUCTION

The notion of Semantic Web has been gaining significance in healthcare domain where domain end-users can be considered it as enabler to create precise, unambiguous encoding of information in a machine readable format [1]. The semantic web is known as the platform that brings a set of new emerging technologies and models that needs to be found and executed and also promotes integration phenomenon between different data sources using semantic rules, ontologies, web services and web processes [1], [2]. Hence, semantic web is not only considered an application but provides an infrastructure where various data sets such as semantic web standards e.g. FOAF [3], SIOC [4], DBLP [5] etc. can be incorporated underneath single environment for the reusability of already developed vocabularies and ontologies into existing domain ontologies. It also recognized to enhance visibility of knowledge on the web [6] and helps to develop different applications in different businesses especially *B2B E-Commerce, Bio-informatics, Tourism, Personal semantic assistant* [1].

The importance of knowledge reuse is facilitated by the use of explicit ontology which can be used to encode into software systems [7] in different domain e.g. healthcare information systems (HIS) [6]. Here, the semantic web development process can be categorized into many clusters; identification and localization, conceptualization and vocabulary, relationship between semantic tools and axiomatization, tolerant and safe reasoning and facilitating web adoption for extensibility, visibility and inference ability [1], [7]. These characteristics are in semantic web development help to propagate factual knowledge with *link open data (LOD)*. The adoption of *link open data (LOD)* [8] in current study provides more generic, more flexible publishing paradigms of web-based documents which makes it easier for data consumers to discover and integrate data from large number of data sources [9]. In particular, *link open data (LOD)* provides a unifying representation of

data model which relies on RDF data model, a standardized data access mechanism using HTTP protocols pattern over the internet, support hyperlink-based data discovery by using URIs as global identifiers for entities in different data sources and also helps to narrate *Self-descriptive* data for easiness in the integration of data from different sources by relying on shared vocabularies, making the definition of these vocabularies retrievable by allowing terms from different vocabularies to be connected to each other by vocabulary links [9].

This study is based on some observations [10] and *focused to make collaborative networks of practitioners and researchers especially in healthcare organizations. It is bit difficult task to find the most relevant domain experts who have competence in different areas of expertise in different healthcare processes and also involved in healthcare research activities in healthcare institutions.* The main contribution of this paper is to propose the healthcare-oriented collaborative mechanism and standard (collaborative-based ontology architecture) by using semantic web standards e.g. FOAF, SIOC and DBLP which helps to support in collaboration among medical professionals, practitioners and researchers and also represents reusable factual knowledge e.g. vocabularies, ontologies into domain knowledge with the help of *link open data (LOD)*.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly explains the significance of semantic web standards, healthcare vocabularies and ontologies and incorporation of link open data precisely. Section 3 explains in detail about methodology; a collaborative ontology engineering life cycle development process. Section 4 explains about a healthcare social network application. Section 5 shows experiments and results. Section 6 describes discussion and limitation of the study in following sections.

2. CONTEXTUAL BASIS

This section highlights about the semantic web standards and semantic alignment of healthcare oriented FOAF, SIOC and DBLP vocabularies and ontologies and linkage of link open data (LOD) in collaborative ontology development process in healthcare domain.

2.1 Semantic Web Standards: FOAF

The notion of FOAF1 (the friend-of-a-friend) is a machine-readable ontology that describes people, their relations with other entities and activities with other people for building a social networks for specific domain without any centralized database [11]. It is also known as specific schema that is built on top of the RDF which provides a mechanism for people to link with their own developed FOAF files and helps them to define their domain-oriented social networks [11]. FOAF is a descriptive vocabulary based on RDF2 and OWL3 that contains unique Id for any end user e.g. email-address, open-ID, URI, and so on [12]. FOAF helps to use a simple set of modeling constructs for creating extensible, distributed nature of RDF for the propagation of information in distributed environment throughout the web which is supported by a specific community of people [11].

2.2 Semantic Web Standards: SIOC

The notion of SIOC (Semantically-Interlinked Online Communities) aims to enable the linkage and integration of web-based community information of any domain [13]. The combining effort of semantic web technologies and social media paradigms helps to establish social media information spaces where information is socially created and maintained as well as being interlinked with link open data (LOD) using RDF construct [14]. The machine-understandable format of RDF model helps to lead new ways to discover information with respect to information extraction, integration and resolve interoperability issues on the web [14]. SIOC is considered a way for making interaction link between different web entities such as blogs, forums and mailing list that could be easily deployed in existing applications [15].

2.3 Semantic Web Standards: DBLP

The DBLP ontology [16] is developed by Lehigh University by adapting UGA's SwetoDblp Ontology [11], [17] in domain ontology which is basically creates OWL descriptions of the corresponding DBLP concepts that is deployed in ontology-based editor e.g. Top-braid composer. The notion of DBLP also gives support of complete search of publications, people they are involved in different researches, information of authors and co-authors and information of related proceedings, Journal papers, conference papers, editors information and information of different venues at single spot [18].

2.4 Healthcare Vocabularies and Ontologies

In healthcare domain, there are numbers of controlled vocabularies and ontologies can be found on web. These developed ontologies and vocabularies can be reused in

domain ontology development process for the generation of triplets [19]. The advantage of reusability helps to develop comprehensive personalized and dynamic models related to healthcare processes which can be used to support healthcare information system development and semantic web services in healthcare [19]. Some vocabularies and ontologies have been used in healthcare sector such as NCBO BioPortal [20], [21] for an indicative list of overlapped vocabularies, terminologies and ontologies. e.g. 340. Similarly, SNOMED-CT (Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine-Clinical Terms), ICD9/10 (International Statistical Classification Diseases and Related Health Problems), Body System (body system terms used in ICD11), MeSH (Medical Subject Headings), NCI (Meta)Thesaurus, Galen (the high level ontology for the medical domain), HL7 (the Normative RIM model v2), Biomedical Resource Ontology (BRO, a controlled terminology of resources to improve sensitivity and specificity of Web searches) for developing domain model which can be used for developing health information system [19].

2.5 Incorporation of Open Link Data (LOD)

Nowadays, the concept of link open data (LOD) is rapidly becoming the backbone of digital libraries. The idea is that if cross-domain heterogeneous content can be made interoperable in the cloud, then datasets will enrich each other semantically across data silos, enabling more comprehensive and intelligent services for human end-users and web services [22]. It refers to a set of best practices for publishing and connecting structured data on the web that leads to the creation of a global data space containing billions of assertions the web of data [23]. Link open data (LOD) helps to create typed linked between data from different sources in different geographical locations or simply heterogeneous systems within one location [23].

Fig. 1 The Linked Open Data Cloud diagram, by Richard Cyganiak and anja Jentzsch.

From the technical point of view, linked data means to publish data on the web in such a way that can be easily readable by machines and their meanings are explicitly expressed [24]. Link Data changes to organize knowledge based resources on the web can be handled by using four principles; Data are identified by URIs, the URIs can be dereference, the dereference data

contain more useful information about the data and more data are easily discoverable on the web scale [24]. Link Data can be easily queried through SQL4-Like language e.g. SPARQL Query5 [25]. We tried to utilize the concept of Linked Open Data (LOD) in our study in later proceedings.

3. METHODOLOGY

To better understand ontology development process, different ontology development methodologies e.g. METHONTOLOGY [26], TOVE (Toronto Virtual Enterprise) [27] etc. adopt a workflow of specification, conceptualization, implementation and evaluation but they lack collaboration and active involvement of the end-users in healthcare domain [28].

3.1 Collaborative Methodology Using Ontology Patterns

The motive to use collaborative methodology [28] is in our work by defining concrete steps for the development of collaborative ontology in healthcare domain. The most impressive part of this approach is the active engagement of the domain experts in the development of collaborative ontological model especially in specification and conceptualization phase and not just their limited involvement in the model evaluation phase [28]. The collaborative methodology [28] is highly dedicated towards *Healthcare Life Sciences Ontologies* and adopts a “meet-in-the-middle” approach where concepts emerged both in bottom-up approach (i.e. analyzing the domain and interviewing the domain experts regarding their data needs) and top-down (i.e. analyze and integrate existing ontologies, vocabularies and data models) [28]. The concrete steps of the collaborative methodology are discussed in the following phases: specification, top-down and bottom-up conceptualization, inclusion of ontology design patterns (ODPs) [30], implementation and evaluation in (fig. 2).

- a) **Specification:** This phase is dedicated to define the scope of the study and requirements which are core in the development of the semantic model. In this phase, both the ontology engineer and domain experts involve to identify the knowledge for specific domain that should be represented in the semantic model by using different techniques e.g. modeling technique [29], [28]. They contribute their inputs and feedback through brainstorming, interviews and completing questionnaires [28].
- b) **Conceptualization:** This phase highlights the importance of conceptual modeling and identifies different concepts, entities and their relationships among them. The conceptualization phase is based on following sub-sections which helps in ontology conceptualization development process effectively. These sub-sections are described as: *identification of the core concepts* which can be extracted from

the competence questions related to the domain knowledge, *identification of related models and ontologies, analyze them and reuse concepts*, this sub-section is related to find most suitable models and ontologies that can be reused in the target domain that should be investigated with the help of domains experts [28]. This sub-section also emphasis on searching of relevant terms at existing non-ontological resources in the form of lexicons, thesauri, taxonomies and linked datasets [28].

- c) **Inclusion of Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs).** This sub-section supports in conceptualization phase by including *ontology design patterns* (ODPs) which facilitate the modeling of recurrent scenarios and provide guideline for incorporating this knowledge and linked datasets into ontologies correctly [28].
- d) **Implementation:** This phase is focused on, how the conceptual model can be transformed into a computable model using semantic web languages. e.g. OWL, RDF, RDFs etc. Two activities are carried out during the implementation which is very important related to alignment with other models and re-use of upper ontologies [28]. The alignment activity describes the mechanism how other models and ontologies can be incorporated with currently used ontologies by identifying the matching concepts (i.e. have the same or similar meaning), thus enabling their interoperability [28]. Similarly, the re-use of upper ontology activity covers the modeling concepts which are mapped to concepts of an upper (top-level) ontology thus aiding the semantic integration across ontologies [28].

Fig. 2 A Collaborative Methodology for building Ontologies (Zeginis et al., 2013)

- e) **Evaluation:** In this phase, we check developed semantic model fulfils the requirements defined in the specification phase with the help of competence questions. We also test some key

reusability in different domains e.g. healthcare. This work also promotes the collaboration between practitioners, researchers and administrators to achieve quality patient treatment outcomes and emphasis on health-oriented social community.

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